

Seismic Monitoring of Reinforced Concrete Building Using Artificial Neural Network

Taduku Ekambaram¹ and Alope Kumar Datta²

National Institute of Technology Durgapur, India.

Abstract Effective damage diagnosis is required for existing buildings in seismically active region for quick rehabilitation just after earthquake. In this context research on seismic monitoring of Reinforced Concrete (RC) building is gaining importance in recent time. Internal defects to buildings are sometimes unseen, which may cause major failure due to aftershocks. To avoid this type of failure a robust method for diagnose is required. This paper provides an artificial neural network (ANN) based technique for detecting seismic damage in RC building. A feed-forward multilayer neural network with one hidden layer that translates input samples to output parameters makes up the network. The input to the ANN model is considered as key parameters of real-time earthquake ground motion, while the output is considered as key design parameters for seismic safety of structures susceptible to real-time earthquake ground motion. The suggested ANN model is trained using several forms of real-time earthquake ground motion data to provide a suitable range of design parameters based on the seismic safety of particular RC Structure. The model is also tested against new earthquake ground motion data to ensure its applicability and accessibility for seismic health monitoring purposes. A typical RC structure is considered for the development of the model, and numerical simulation is performed using the finite element method to generate the data required for the development of the ANN model. The ANN model is created using MATLAB software, and the results received from this study are encouraging since the ANN model-based seismic structural health monitoring may be rapid and efficient. The suggested technique may be utilized to efficiently monitor post-earthquake health of RC buildings, which is critical for any such structures.

Key Words: Structural Health Monitoring, Earthquake Ground Motion, Finite Element Method, Time History Analysis, Artificial Neural Network.

Introduction

Infrastructure development, which plays a key part in raising economic status, has a significant impact on a country's economy and progress. The more infrastructure there is, the better the country will develop. Large democracies, such as India, have a very large economy, and the flow of that economy is dependent on public infrastructures. However, after constructing such infrastructure and putting it into public service, it is left unmonitored and unmaintained after a certain period of time, resulting in the collapse of the structure, the loss of human lives, and the loss of various services that boost the economy. Every structure requires maintenance and structural health monitoring on a regular basis [1,2]. The Structural Health Monitoring of seismic vulnerability of existing RC buildings is an important structural engineering subject that is being researched internationally. The fact that the great majority of current RC buildings are concentrated in metropolitan cities. This necessitates an assessment of their seismic risk. This Structural Health Monitoring informs the decision on the need for seismic retrofitting. Furthermore, the capacity to swiftly (in real time) quantify the seismic susceptibility of several structures following a major earthquake is critical, and this necessitates a rapid evaluation of the earthquake-induced damage. This estimate gives crucial information to emergency responders regarding the most severely affected areas. As a result, the seismic risk assessment problem might affect either a single structure or a group of buildings [3]. Morfidis and Kostinakis, developed an ANN model for predicting maximum inter-story drift ratio given 14 seismic parameters of ground motion attributes and 4 structure factors. Multilayer Feed-forward Perceptron networks were employed in both the Stepwise Method and the Backward Stepwise Method. For the training data set of the ANNs, 30 RC structures with varying structural characteristics that were subjected to 65 real ground motions were selected [4]. Chia-Ming Chang, Structural health monitoring is required to interpret damaged structures in terms of location and severity, as well as the remaining performance of the damaged portions. As a consequence, based on neural network modeling, this study proposes a new artificial intelligence-based structural health monitoring approach [5]. Oliver Richard de Lautour, the damage indices were predicted using artificial neural networks (ANN) based on structural nonlinear dynamic response data of 2D reinforcement concrete (RC) frame structures with varying topology, stiffness, strength, and damping, with 13 structural parameters and 6 ground shaking parameters used as inputs [6]. Sayyed Mohsen Vazirizade, localization and measurement of structural damage, as well as failure probability determination, are important outputs in structural reliability evaluation. In this study, an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is used to reduce the processing effort required for reliability analysis and damage detection [7]. Hoang D. Nguyen, ANN Model and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) techniques were used to predict the maximum top drift and maximum inter-story drift for planar steel frames based on ground motion intensity, earthquake and soil types, 5%-critical-damped spectral accelerations corresponding to the first three self-vibration periods of structures, and structural geometric configurations [8]. Byung Kwan Oh, proposed a new parameter called resonance area to characterize the frequency domain relationship between ground motion records and a target structure, and used it as input along with ground motion characteristic parameters to build a neural network-based model to predict the maximum seismic inter-story drift ratio and maximum seismic displacement of a building [9]. Reni Suryanita, ANN models were used to estimate the structure's acceleration, velocity, and displacement response in different directions based on the database generated by modal response spectrum analysis, using seismic parameters, site conditions, and

building geometry parameters as inputs [10].

Simulating Building Response Data: A Numerical Approach

2 storey 3D frame structure undergo dynamic analysis in line with IS Code 1893 (Part-1):2016. Either the Time History Analysis approach or the Response Spectrum method is employed for dynamic analysis. The current study employs ETABS software and time history analysis to assess a 2-storey 3D RC frame building. The 2-storey 3D frame RC Structure by Earthquakes ground excitations used for time history analysis as shown in Table 1. Figures. 1a-f illustrates Several earthquakes ground motion time history graphs.

Table 1. Earthquakes used for time history analysis

Earthquake Name	Station Name	Fault Type	PGA(g)	Year	Magnitude
Borrego Mtn	El Centro Array #9	Shallow strike-slip	0.133	1968	6.63
Cape Mendocino	Fortuna - Fortuna Blvd	Strike-slip fault	0.106	1992	7.01
Cape Mendocino	Shelter Cove Airport	Strike-slip fault	0.228	1992	7.01
Chi-Chi, Taiwan-03	TCU115	Active normal fault	0.052	1999	6.2
Coalinga-01	Parkfield - Fault Zone 2	Strike-slip fault	0.118	1983	6.36
Corinth, Greece	Corinth	Active normal fault	0.237	1981	6.6
Duzce, Turkey	Lamont 362	Right-lateral strike-slip fault	0.025	1999	7.14
Duzce, Turkey	Lamont 1061	Right-lateral strike-slip fault	0.119	1999	7.14
Imperial Valley-06	Cerro Prieto	Strike-slip fault	0.160	1979	6.53
Iwate	Yuzawa Town	Strike-slip fault	0.159	2008	6.9
Iwate	Machimukai Town	Strike-slip fault	0.145	2008	6.9
Kobe, Japan	Tadoka	Strike-slip fault	0.250	1995	6.9
Landers	Joshua Tree	Strike-slip fault	0.274	1992	7.28
Manjil, Iran	Abbar	Left-lateral strike-slip fault	0.515	1990	7.37
Northridge-01	Camarillo	Strike-slip fault	0.124	1994	6.69
Northridge-01	Sunland - Mt Gleason Ave	Strike-slip fault	0.133	1994	6.69
Humbolt Bay	Ferndale City Hall	Strike-slip fault	0.032	1937	5.8
Imperial Valley-01	El Centro Array #9	Strike-slip fault	0.012	1938	5
Northwest Calif-01	Ferndale City Hall	Strike-slip fault	0.150	1938	5.5
Imperial Valley-03	El Centro Array #9	Strike-slip fault	0.029	1951	5.6
Northwest Calif-03	Ferndale City Hall	Strike-slip fault	0.108	1951	5.8

(a) Borrego Mtn Earthquake ground acceleration

(b) Imperial Valley-06 Earthquake ground acceleration

Department of C

(c) Cape Mendocino Earthquake ground acceleration

(d) Chi-Chi, Taiwan-03 Earthquake ground acceleration

(e) Kobe, Japan Earthquake ground acceleration

(f) Duzce, Turkey Earthquake ground acceleration

Fig 1. Several earthquakes ground motion time history graphs

The maximum permissible displacement, base shear, and maximum inter storey drift of a two-story three-dimensional frame structure is examined. The study and modeling of the complete structure are carried out using the well-known FEM integrated software ETABS [11], in accordance with the seismic zones of India used by IS 1893 (Part-1) 2016. Applied load cases are Dead Load (self-weight of beam and column), Earthquake Load in x-direction and y-direction.

Table 2. Building Details

Designation	Range	Designation	Range
Height of the building	7 m	Grade of concrete	M30
Floor to Floor height (GF, FF)	4m,3m	Grade of steel	FE 415
Damping	5%	Plan	36 m2
Support conditions	fixed	Importance Factor, I	1
Beam size	400 × 500 (mm)	Column size	500 × 500 (mm)

The paper focuses on a two-story three-dimensional frame structure (figures 2a and 2b) as a case study for dynamic analysis using Time History Analysis. The dynamic analysis in the ETABS software determines the natural frequencies and time period of the two-story 3D frame building, as shown in Table-2. The natural frequencies are used as a reference to identify the potential earthquake ground motion that could cause damage to the structure. The Fast Fourier Transformation method is employed to determine the frequency domain of different earthquake ground motions. The frequency domain of the ground motion is then compared to the natural frequency of the structure to determine if they match, it is crucial to match these frequencies as the structure ground motion coincides with its natural frequency can be conducted. Once a suitable earthquake ground motion is selected, non-linear dynamic parameters such as acceleration, displacement, and velocity of the structure are analyzed. Finally, the Fast Fourier Transformation technique is used to analyze the frequency of the nodes, a suitable position for SHM can be identified. Damage to the structure is directly proportional to the frequency range to monitor the structure's health is critical. The node for the Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) is critical.

Once a design chosen, Finally, can be appropriate critical

(a) (b)

Fig 2. 2(a) Plan view in ETABS, 2(b) 3D view in ETABS

Table 3. Modal Periods and Natural Frequencies of structure

Case	Mode	Period	Frequency
unitless	unitless	sec	cyc/sec
Modal	1	0.190	5.248
Modal	2	0.190	5.248
Modal	3	0.173	5.756
Modal	4	0.0518	19.299
Modal	5	0.0518	19.299
Modal	6	0.0491	20.338

Several types of ground motion data are collected for time history analysis. On each of the provided ground motion data, the referenced time domain data is then transformed into the frequency domain using Fast Fourier Transformation. FFT analysis is performed using the MATLAB program.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)

The artificial neural network (ANN) is a mathematical model based on the biological neural network. The ANN system is made up of many processing layers and neurons. The connection and signal transmission between neurons and layers, much as in a biological neural network, allow the ANN system to turn the supplied input signal into acceptable outputs, which is subsequently referred to as prediction. ANN can predict output based on any given input, even if the mathematical connection between the input and output parameter is nonlinear and complicated. An input layer, a hidden layer, and an output layer compose a multi-layer ANN system. The input layer is made up of neurons that receive external signals (input data). The hidden layer also includes neurons that receive signals from input neurons and send them to the output layer. The number of neurons in the hidden layer influences the prediction rate and the ANN system's capacity to deal with nonlinear relationships between variables. Finally, the output layer is made up of output neurons that reflect the projected output parameters. The error of the ANN system is the difference between the projected output value and the target value. Before the ANN is ready for testing, it must first be trained using a collection of data. The trained ANN system is anticipated to be able to predict outputs with reasonable accuracy based on any given inputs. Mean-Squared Error (MSE) and Coefficient of Correlation (R) are two often used metrics for assessing the performance of an ANN system. In this study, it is suggested to use ANN on a two-story three-dimensional frame structure exposed to various ground motions. Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA), Peak Ground Velocity (PGV), Peak Ground Displacement (PGD), Frequency, and Duration were measured for the two-story three-dimensional frame building. The numerical simulation of structural reactions was performed using the FEM integrated program ETABS with Time History Analysis. During the training phase, an input is selected from a set of known input-output pairings, and the network is trained. The Levenberg-Marquardt method is employed in this paper to minimize error [12]. All ANN applications were performed using the MATLAB Neural Network Toolbox [13].

ANN Modelling of Earthquake Ground Motion and Structural Parameters

In this study 8 parameters were used for ANN model, 5 parameters for ground motion and 4 parameters for structural design parameters. The ground motion parameters were (i) peak Ground Acceleration (PGA), (ii) peak Ground Velocity (PGV), (iii) peak Ground Displacement (PGD), (iv) Ground Motion Frequency, (v) Time Duration. Table-4 shows adopted values for parameters (i)-(iv) and (v) are earthquake ground motion peak values and effective time duration of ground motions respectively. The earthquake ground motions are collected from PEER Ground Motion Database [14]. The data set was constructed using 20 earthquake recordings to guarantee that the network learned the combination of characteristics that causes damage. The three structural parameters were (i) Max. Displacement, (ii) Max. Inter-Story Drift, (iii) Structural Critical Node Frequency, (iv) Base Shear. After performing Time History Analysis in FEM software ETABS, we get structural response parameters, they are outputs for training artificial neural network (ANN) model. The parameters of these structural responses are given in Table-5.

Table 4. Parameters of earthquake ground motions, inputs for ANN Model

Earthquake Name	PGA g	PGV cm/sec ²	PGD cm	Time Duration sec	Frequency Hz
Borrego Mtn	0.133	19.852	14.6	79.98	0.612
Cape Mendocino	0.106	19.600	29.040	43.98	0.341
Cape Mendocino	0.228	6.461	0.388	35.98	6.197
Chi-Chi, Taiwan-03	0.052	15.896	12.070	74.995	0.413
Coalinga-01	0.118	23.521	6.881	59.98	0.7
Corinth, Greece	0.237	22.944	5.719	41.31	1.839
Duzce, Turkey	0.025	5.949	8.082	43.15	1.622
Duzce, Turkey	0.119	12.123	8.774	42.32	3.189
Imperial Valley-06	0.160	11.549	5.239	63.81	2.35
Iwate	0.159	27.385	9.035	59.99	0.683
Iwate	0.145	39.960	21.593	61.99	0.306
Kobe, Japan	0.250	24.477	7.584	139.99	3.907
Landers	0.274	27.007	7.703	43.98	0.773
Manjil, Iran	0.515	39.051	14.862	53.5	2.71
Northridge-01	0.124	10.004	3.435	64.98	1.246
Northridge-01	0.133	15.722	4.247	29.98	1.634
Humbolt Bay	0.032	2.363	0.346	39.995	1.725
Imperial Valley-01	0.012	0.550	0.053	30	6.666
Northwest Calif-01	0.150	6.122	0.491	39.995	3.275
Imperial Valley-03	0.029	2.726	0.434	39.995	2.25
Northwest Calif-03	0.108	4.658	0.544	39.995	2.625

Training of ANN Model

After the generation of input and output data. This was randomly divided into 70% for training, 15% for validation, and 15% for testing the ANN Model. A two-layer feed-forward network with sigmoid hidden neurons and linear output neurons will be employed in this study, and the network will be trained using the Levenberg-Marquardt backpropagation technique. Use Mean Square Error and Regression Analysis to assess its performance. For training, 20 samples of 5 elements from the input layer and 20 samples of 4 elements from the output layer were obtained. In this scenario, just one hidden layer is examined, and six neurons are used in the hidden layer by trial-and-error method.

Fig 3. Architecture of ANN Model

Table 5. Parameters of structural responses, outputs for ANN Model

Earthquake Name	Frequency Hz	MISD mm/mm	Displacement mm	Base Shear kN
-----------------	-----------------	---------------	--------------------	------------------

Borrego Mtn	5.313	0.000273	1.816	54.97
Cape Mendocino	5.295	0.000353	2.203	70.57
Cape Mendocino	5.25	0.001282	8.646	248.64
Chi-Chi, Taiwan-03	5.093	0.000165	1.104	27.73
Coalinga-01	5.1	0.000337	2.248	60.02
Corinth, Greece	5.493	0.000599	3.961	96.88
Duzce, Turkey	5.375	0.000088	0.601	16.10
Duzce, Turkey	5.197	0.000481	3.24	95.48
Imperial Valley-06	5.296	0.000652	4.355	129.69
Iwate	5.083	0.00058	3.852	88.16
Iwate	5.096	0.000689	3.701	136.27
Kobe, Japan	5.514	0.00205	13.891	395.23
Landers	5.272	0.000723	3.565	147.15
Manjil, Iran	5.231	0.002793	18.573	562.14
Northridge-01	5.461	0.000362	2.435	61.66
Northridge-01	5.201	0.000499	3.349	96.29
Humbolt Bay	5.175	0.000145	0.974	20.24
Imperial Valley-01	5.232	0.000087	0.591	16.32
Northwest Calif-01	5.4	0.000517	3.435	103.39
Imperial Valley-03	5.375	0.000103	0.698	18.01
Northwest Calif-03	5.275	0.000506	3.404	99.76

Performance of ANN Model

An ANN model's performance is evaluated using Mean Square Error (MSE) and Regression Analysis. The smaller the MSE, the better the performance of the ANN for regression tasks. When compared to the actual values in the dataset, a lower MSE indicates that the model's predictions are more accurate. High MSE values suggest that the model's predictions are far off the mark. Higher R values are usually preferred since they indicate that the model is capable of predicting outcomes. In this situation, the trained ANN model yielded less Mean Square Error (MSE = 0.53949), shown in Figure-5. That is, the trained ANN model predicts correctly, and the trained ANN model has a better Regression Analysis (R=0.99486) value, as shown in Figure-4.

Fig 4. Regression Analysis

Fig 5. Mean Square Error (MSE)

Comparing Results ETABS and Artificial Neural Networks in Predicting Structural Responses

In this case, the ANN model was trained using input and output data from 20 earthquakes. The trained ANN model predicted the structural characteristics of a two-story three-dimensional frame structure (max. displacement, maximum inter story drift, structural frequency, and base shear) using new ground motion data (Northwest Calif-03, Ferndale City Hall in 1951) given in Table-6. The structural Parameters from FE software (ETABS) was then compared to the predicted structural parameter from the trained ANN model are shown in Table-7. Comparison of structural parameters from ANN model and FE software (ETABS) are shown in graphical representation (figure 6).

Table 6. New ground motion data

Earthquake Name	PGA g	PGV cm/sec ²	PGD cm	Time Duration sec	Frequency Hz
Northwest Calif-03	0.108	4.658	0.544	39.995	2.625

Table 7. Compared structural Parameters from ETABS to trained ANN model

	Frequency Hz	MISD mm/mm	Displacement mm	Base Shear kN
ETABS	5.275	0.000506	3.404	99.76
ANN Model	5.2391	0.000428	3.056	108.05

Fig 6. Comparison of structural parameters from ANN model and FE software (ETABS)

Conclusion

A systematic numerical simulation research was carried out to demonstrate the efficacy of an ANN model under the domain of Artificial Intelligence for Seismic Structural Health Monitoring of a two-story three-dimensional frame structure. The investigation's findings are as follows:

- This research describes a numerical simulation study targeted at performing health monitoring of a two-story three-dimensional frame structure after earthquakes of different magnitudes and locations.
- To create the ANN model, real-time earthquake ground motion data was used to acquire acceleration response records at critical locations, especially on the top level of the structure.
- As monitoring parameters, important parameters from Earthquake Ground Motion data (PGA, PGV, PGD, Duration, Earthquake Frequency) were utilized as input, while key design parameters (Structural Frequency, Maximum Displacement, Maximum Inter-Story Drift, Base Shear) were used as output.
- Seismic structural health monitoring relies on frequency estimation from response records as the most effective approach to assess a structure's in-situ health following earthquakes.
- The model can perform effectively in predicting out-put as monitoring parameter in less time than the conventional approach.
- AI model-based approach can be very efficient in Seismic Structural Health Monitoring as it does not require the physical model-based approach.

References

1. Farrar, C. R., & Worden, K. (2007), "An introduction to structural health monitoring", *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 365:303-315.
2. Abrardo, A., Balucanti, L., Belleschi, M., Carretti, C. M., & Mecocci, A. (2010), "Health monitoring of architectural heritage: The case study of San Gimignano", In *2010 IEEE workshop on environmental energy and structural monitoring systems*, 98-102.
3. American Society of Civil Engineering. (2007, May). Seismic rehabilitation of existing buildings. American Society of Civil Engineers.
4. Morfidis, K., & Kostinakis, K. (2018), "Approaches to the rapid seismic damage prediction of r/c buildings using artificial neural networks", *Engineering Structures*, 165:120–141.
5. Chang, C.-M., Lin, T.-K., & Chang, C.-W. (2018), "Applications of neural network models for structural health monitoring based on derived modal properties", *Measurement*, 129:457–470.
6. De Lautour, O. R., & Omenzetter, P. (2009), "Prediction of seismic-induced structural damage using artificial neural networks", *Engineering Structures*, 31:600–606.
7. Vazirizade, S. M., Nozhati, S., & Zadeh, M. A. (2017), "Seismic reliability assessment of structures using artificial neural network", *Journal of Building Engineering*, 11:230–235.
8. Nguyen, H. D., Dao, N. D., & Shin, M. (2021), "Prediction of seismic drift responses of planar steel moment frames using artificial neural network and extreme gradient boosting", *Engineering Structures*, 242:112518.
9. Oh, B. K., Glisic, B., Park, S. W., & Park, H. S. (2019), "Neural network-based seismic response prediction model for building structures using artificial earthquakes", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 115109.
10. Suryanita, R., Maizir, H., & Jingga, H. (2016), "Prediction of structural response due to earthquake load using artificial neural networks", In *Int. Conf. Eng. Technol. Comput. Basic Appl. Sci. ECBA, 2016, Osaka, Japan*, 182.
11. Computers & Structures, Inc., (2016), User's Guide ETABS® 2016 Integrated Building Design Software, Structural and Earthquake Engineering Software.

12. Marquardt, D. W. (1963), "An Algorithm for Least-Squares Estimation of Nonlinear Parameters", Journal of the Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, 11:431–441.
13. Demuth HB, Beale MH, Hagan MT (2006), Neural network toolbox 5, User's guide, Natick (MA), Math works.